

D2D CRC Law and Policy Deliverable D.C3.3

***DC25008: Compliance by Design (CbD) and
Compliance through Design (CtD).
Solutions to support automated information
sharing.***

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Deliverable D.C3.3

Natural Language Processing and Semantic Tools: A Roadmap towards publishing law as data

By Víctor Rodríguez-Doncel

Independent research report commissioned by the Australian Criminal
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Acronyms

API	Application Programming Interface
CbD	Compliance by Design
CtD	Compliance through Design
D2D CRC	Data to Decisions Cooperative Research Centre
DOI	Document Object Identifier
ECLI	European Case Law Identifier
ELI	European Legislation Identifier
LDA	Latent Dirichlet Allocation
LII	Legal Information Institute
NLP	Natural Language Processing
RDF	Resource Description Framework
SKOS	Simple Knowledge Organization System
TF-IDF	Term frequency – Inverse Document Frequency
TTL	Terse RDF Triple Language

Executive Summary

Australian Federal Legislation is published by the Federal Register of Legislation with an open license but in formats difficult to be processed by computers. Text mining and NLP algorithms need this collection to be offered as plain text file, semantic technologies need the information to be structured and interoperable. This deliverable proposes a roadmap towards publishing law as data and describes early results of a sketch implementation. As a result of this effort, a corpus with 884 principal Acts in force as of 29 December 2018 (Australian Federal Legislation) has been generated. The dataset can be referenced, is permanently online (with DOI [10.5281/zenodo.2528149](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.2528149)) and is offered in two forms (1) as pure txt documents (2) as RDF Turtle documents following the ELI schema (European Legislation Identifier ontology).

1. Introduction

1.1 Introduction

The work presented in this document has been made as part of Project C, “Compliance by Design (CbD) and Compliance through Design (CtD) solutions to support automated information sharing”, within the Law and Policy Program, Data to Decisions Cooperative Research Centre (D2D CRC).

This deliverable describes a possible approach to integrate these solutions, proposes a roadmap and describes a first prototype to illustrate the benefits.

1.2 Approach for the integration of CbD and CtD

The Use Cases on spent convictions scheme in the different states of the Commonwealth serve well to illustrate the limitations and benefits of the CbD and CtD approaches. More information on CbD and CtD can be found in a survey (Hashmi et al. 2018) and in CRC Deliverable C3.2.

In each of the use cases analysed in the Deliverable D3.1 and D3.5, a decision has to be taken as to whether or not release a criminal record. These decisions are taken in consideration of certain parameters and circumstances and it is well described in Deliverable D3.4. Some of these considerations are explicit, precise and digitised (e.g. the age of the person whose criminal record is to be released), other considerations are vague and depend on a fuzzy consideration (reintegration into society, nature of the crime).

Before any information is released, a decision path is followed in which some of the steps can be fully automated and some others need human appraisal. Rule based systems (which are a good example of CbD systems) can be considered to address the fully automated ones, but in other circumstances it remains in the hands of human discretion. CtD systems can also assist humans in their decision making by providing related documents which broaden the scope and consider contextual information. They followed the general pragmatic trend described for the web of linked data in Casanovas, Rodríguez-Doncel and González-Conejero (2017).

Recent technological developments are enabling new systems which might be classified as CtD. For example, cognitive computing systems based on IBM Watson can tackle millions of text documents and extract effective knowledge from them to assist in decision-making processes. With both CtD and cognitive computing systems, machines consider context in a manner more similar to humans. Also, new chatbot technologies enable fluent interaction between humans and machines to merge the benefits of each approach.

This deliverable describes a sub-project along these lines with the purpose to provide better access to legal information using semantic web technologies.

Semantic Web technologies are a step closer to CtD in the sense that these systems are not fully agnostic of the context, which can be better related with linked data and which use standard vocabularies and ontologies. The specific technological proposition is that legal information systems can be improved if the pool of documents is structured in a Semantic Web manner, and that this structure propitiates less ambiguities, better search and faster information retrieval. Thus, the precise scope of this work is the transformation of some documents into RDF structures.

2. Objectives and scope

1.3 Objectives

The **general objective** of this sub-project is to describe the scope of application of the CbD and CtD approaches. Both Compliance by Design and Compliance through Design are useful and can complement each other in practical settings.

The **specific objective** of this sub-project is the creation of a web portal for the search of legal information related to spent-convictions through heterogeneous publication formats.

Derived **sub-objectives** are to:

- Harvest a small collection of heterogeneous documents sufficient to test cross document-type search.
- Transform the documents into text form (TXT), so that homogeneous processing can be done.
- Transform the key metadata elements of the documents into an RDF form, following a *law as data* policy, with the minimal structure to demonstrate better performance than the standard legal information providers.
- Create a web portal where a text query can be made, and relevant documents retrieved.

1.4 Scope

Whereas the number of documents related to spent convictions is very limited due to their nature, a greater number of documents has been considered so that the achievement of objectives can be sufficiently demonstrated. In particular, the following documents have been deemed as of interest by D3.6 and other deliverables.

Case law was first searched in Lexis Advance as described in D3.6.

id	title
	Earl Seymour Davis v Clive James Murray, 23 December 1993

	Earl Seymour Davis v Commonwealth Director of Public Prosecutions, unreported, 21 April 1994
	VX96A v Insurance and Superannuation Commissioner (1996) 23 AAR 427
	AA, Re; Australian Prudential Regulation Authority [2001] AATA 979
336	VWOK v Minister for Immigration and Multicultural and Indigenous Affairs [2005] FCA 336; [2005] FCAFC 249
	Seymour v Migration Agents Registration Board [2007] FCAFC 76
	Hartwig v PE Hack, Deputy President, Administrative Appeals Tribunal [2007] FCA 1039
286	Xerxes Behram Surty v John Keith Bowyer [2009] WASC 286
765	Volonski v Migration Agents Registration Board [2010] AATA 765
	Porter, Re; Application under the Superannuation Industry (Supervision) Act 1993 [2012] FCA 1431
	Frugtniet v Tax Practitioners Board [2013] FCA 752; [2015] FCA 1066; [2017] AATA 1393
128	Frugtniet v Australian Securities and Investments Commission [2015] AATA 128; [2016] FCA 995; [2017] FCAFC 162

Table 1. Cases identified in D3.6

3. Related work

Commonwealth legislation is published by the Federal Register of Legislation¹ (formerly ComLaw), and it is available in PDF and Microsoft Word formats.

Whereas the use of Semantic Web technologies in the legal domain is not new (see Casanovas et al., 2016 for a broad panorama), the adoption of these technologies in the legal domain has only become widespread recently. New start-ups are offering private tools (see Ross Intelligence, which also use semantic techniques), legislation publishers are also adopting structured schemas, and new EU-funded research projects have hatched (BOECLI², EUCases³, Lynx⁴) demonstrating the uses of publishing *law as data*.

With respect to legislation, official publishers have been encoded it using Metalex in the UK or in the Netherlands, with LexDania in Denmark (Petersen 2011), with CHLexML in Switzerland, with NormeInRete in Italy, or with Akoma Ntoso in the USA [AKN, in the USA wording]. Other non-official initiatives have also offered Finnish (Frosterus et al. 2013) and Greek (Chalkdis et al. 2017) legislation as Linked Data.

¹ See <https://www.legislation.gov.au/>

² <http://bo-ecli.eu>

³ <http://eucases.eu>

⁴ <http://lynx-project.eu>

At the European level, the Publications Office of the EU maintains the CELLAR repository for storing official publications and bibliographic resources produced by the different institutions of the EU (Francesconi et al. 2015). Not surprisingly, the information is also available through SPARQL endpoints. However, these systems have the ambition to mirror the legislator's texts and they cannot offer enhanced versions with added contents or links, which therefore falls into the realm of private companies.

A number of European Union member states have implemented or are implementing the European Legislation Identifier (ELI). ELI is based on three ideas, namely, (a) using a well-defined identifier, (b) defining metadata records and (c) organising them with an ontology. ELI permits accessing of legal resources in a homogeneous manner throughout the jurisdictions, describing the metadata records in a similar fashion in RDF and offering an integrated access to the different expressions of the same document (different languages, different formats). This means legal resources are identified in the same manner in France, United Kingdom, Italy, Luxembourg, Ireland or Denmark, just to name a few.

Australia lags behind in the area of publishing structured legislation online. Legal information in Australia is offered by the different States and federal territories of the Commonwealth, but no structure is given by any the Australian authorities, which merely publish legislation as Word/RTF, HTML or PDF documents.

Other non-EU member states have shown interest (Albania, Norway, Switzerland) for the identification of legal resources with an URI template as in ELI. If Australia embraced this policy, it could be accommodated. For example, the Australian 'Regional Investment Corporation Act 2018, No. 6, 2018' would be uniquely identified as:

<http://server-dependant-part.au/eli/au/a/2018/6/en/rdf>

The server-dependant -part would change (perhaps in a domain hosted in La Trobe), and then the next parts would identify *Australia* (referring to Commonwealth law), *act* (*a* stands for Act), 2018 (year), 6 (number), *en* (English). The ending *rdf* would be the format (txt, pdf, etc.) and would not be mandatory⁵.

A similar policy to harmonize identifiers is being also followed in Europe with respect to case law: the European Case Law Identifier (ECLI). Countries that have adopted ECLI include Germany, Italy, Belgium, Greece, Estonia or the Czech Republic, among others.

4. Legal restrictions

The copyright status of information published by the Federal Register of Legislation can be ascertained online.⁶ Fortunately, "*most of the content on*

⁵ To show a second example, see the ELI of a real, existing act in Luxemburg.

<http://eli.legilux.public.lu/eli/etat/leg/rgd/2009/12/10/n1>

⁶ <https://www.legislation.gov.au/Content/Disclaimer#copyright>

the Legislation Register can be freely used under a Creative Commons licence”, and this license is CC-BY 4.0, namely, transformation of the resource and re-publication is possible as long as the original source of information is mentioned, in the following manner:

[Y]ou provide a link to the relevant pages on the Legislation Register or, if multiple pages are involved, a link to the Legislation Register home page; and you attribute the content to the Federal Register of Legislation, provide a link to the CC licence, and indicate if any changes were made. You may do so in any reasonable manner, but not in any way that suggests we endorse you or your use.

The Federal Register of Legislation requests for a polite use of their services, however. In their recommendations for software developers, they comment⁷:

Automated processes can be used to download or spider (crawl) this website, but please respect the crawl-delay instruction in our robots.txt file.

The recommended querying ratio is 1 query every 10 seconds, attending to the file available under <https://www.legislation.gov.au/robots.txt>. Note that downloading the entire collection of acts in force as of today, would require about half a day of processing –abuses of which may receive a penalty.

Please note that the policy of Legal Institutes, such as Austlii, is restrictive and would not allow the tasks envisaged for this project. As stated in their copyright information page ⁸ (Section 4), where “spidering or other automated collection for these purposes is apparent, it will be blocked”.

5. Roadmap

5.1 Roadmap

The allocated resources for this project are not sufficient for a full demonstration, yet they are sufficient so as to establish an initial prototype.

Figure 1 describes the steps towards achieving advanced functionalities, CtD, based on the ‘law as data’.

⁷ <https://www.legislation.gov.au/Content/Linking>

⁸ <http://www.austlii.edu.au/copyright.html>

Figure 1. Roadmap for the publication of Law as Data and the development of advanced functionalities

1. *Document harvesting* refers to the collection of documents relevant to the domain in question, namely, spent convictions. This harvesting stage is made by spidering official publishers which allow transformation and republication of content.
Every document source requires the development of specific code to make the document download, either by querying an API, by web scrapping or by other means.
2. *Document transformation* refers to the process of parsing the documents in their original form (PDF, RTF, Word, HTML) and transforming them to: (a) their pure text form and (b) an RDF form. Transforming documents to text format is necessary for NLP algorithms to operate, whereas transforming them into RDF is necessary for their integration in the Web of Data. This sub-project proposes using the European approach and adopting the ELI metadata records and the ELI ontology.
3. *Document analysis* refers to the enrichment of structured resources with annotations, links and other information elements of interest. For example, annotations can link key concepts to the concepts of compliance (see
4. Figure 2). As a subtask of this stage, the concepts should be arranged in an SKOS thesaurus.
5. *Portal development* refers to the minimal interface necessary to serve the documents as data, both in their TXT and RDF form. Once integrated, the legislative instrument is published as data, ready for others to provide advanced analysis services. This sub-project proposes using the European approach and adopting the ELI URI template.

Figure 2. Sample of the draft work by Casanovas and Hashmi (2019), on categorising concepts

5.2. Expected Impact

The impact of this sub-project in the mid and long term is twofold:

- Strictly related to this project, the outcome might reveal the value of offering legislation as RDF and the value of CtD approaches which rely on densely connected data. This is the first step towards a legal institutional design that can show the appropriateness of semantic web approaches to ground practical institutional design for LEAs, agencies, legal policies etc.
- As a side impact, this initiative will be the first, up to our knowledge, publishing the legal information as RDF, adopting the latest W3C recommendations, and tuned with other related initiatives in the US and Europe.

Example of application: a better search

«Standard legal information portals (either authoritative or not) enable text search. However, they can be improved if the documents in the platform have been enriched as described in the Section before. Thus, a search on the term ‘civil rights’ in standard LII servers, will most likely not return any document not explicitly mentioning that term. However, in the documents enriched by the SKOS thesaurus, the simple inference would also return documents lacking reference to ‘civil rights’ but including reference to the terms ‘freedom of expression’ or ‘fair trial and effective remedy’ (see blue box in Figure 2).»

Second example of application: better indexing by Google

«Based on the ELI ontology, the forthcoming schema.org metadata elements describing legislation (<https://pending.schema.org/Legislation>) will enable more intelligent presentation by Google and other search engines. (see example in Figure 3)»

The image shows a Google search interface for the query "directive 1980/181".

Today: The current search results are a list of three links from EUR-Lex. Each result includes the document title, a breadcrumb trail (eur-lex.europa.eu > EUROPA > EU law and publications > EUR-Lex), and a brief description of the document. The first result is "EUR-Lex - 31980L0181 - EN - EUR-Lex" for Council Directive 80/181/EEC. The second is "EUR-Lex - 01980L0181-19841220 - EN - EUR-Lex" for Council Directive 80/181/EEC. The third is "1980/181/EEC - EUR-Lex - Europa.eu" for Council Directive 71/354/EEC.

Tomorrow ? A proposed smart metadata description is shown in a pink box. It features a prominent title "EUR-Lex – 31980L0181 – EN – EUR-Lex" and a detailed description: "Council Directive of 20 December 1979 on the approximation of the laws of the Member States relating to units of measures ...". It also includes status information: "Status : Currently in force" and "About : metrology, measuring equipment, approximation of laws". At the bottom, it provides links for "Original version (20/12/1979)" and "latest consolidation (27/05/2009)".

Figure 3. Smart metadata description of legal resources will enable better presentation by Google and others

5.3. Extended analysis

Once the platform is ready, a number of future developments are possible. To name just a few:

- a) Recommendation of documents, based on topics modelling techniques (Blei et al. 2003, Bastani et al. 2018). This can only be done once the platform is ready and the documents are homogeneously accessible as text.
- b) Recommendation of documents based on graph metrics (e.g. number of shared links, etc). This can only be done once the platform is ready and the documents are linked to references in a machine-readable form.
- c) Accessing and visualising legislation over time, graphically. This can only be done once provenance chains can be established by having documents uniquely identified and with provenance information.

6. Early results

Even if within the scope of this project the described roadmap cannot be fully implemented, at the least a first assessment of each step and a glimpse of first results will be seen. This section describes the major results for each step.

6.1. Document harvesting

The need for documents is not limited to those related to the spent conviction cases. In order to determine the relevance of each word in each of the relevant documents (case law related to spent convictions, for example), it is also necessary to have a large base of documents, related if possible, so that the specific relevance of each term can be ascertained.

Given the legal restrictions imposed on the access to Austlii and other payed sources, no attempt to download large portions of data from Austlii was made. Instead, and in order to train neutral data models for Australian legislation, a large download of Federal legislation was made.

The Federal Register of Legislation publishes legislation under the following URL:

<https://www.legislation.gov.au>

There is no massive data download available from the portal, and to the best of the author's knowledge, there is no other massive download point. However, nothing prevents, neither legally (see Section 0) nor technically, the massive download of data.

Legislation is in general offered as PDF, Open Office XML (with extension .docx, native of Microsoft Word) and a version of the former compressed as a zip file.

The massive download of Australian legislation from the Federal Register of Legislation is not straightforward, as there is no index of documents, nor do they follow a logical sequence. Moreover, the documents (PDF, ZIP, DOCX) are not offered at any logical URL, but with a hash that makes cumbersome the systematic download. As an additional hurdle, navigation is not reflected in the URLs and the system is not stateless.

Principal legislation in force as of December 2018 was considered, and 1175 Acts were found by a spider program developed *ad hoc*, capable of browsing per each pair of letters of the format:

`base/Browse/Results/ByTitle/Acts/InForce/Na/0/0/principal.`

Results are offered paginated, in groups of 50. Manual correction was necessary for those pair of letters yielding more than 50 documents. Given the relatively small number of documents, the 10 seconds between download were reduced to only 1. The entire download procedure, carried out during the Australian night, took about 147 minutes.

6.2. Document transformation

Parsing the DOCX is a task prone to errors, especially when the format of the acts varies with the years. Many of the documents were not available as .zip, some were

only available in the private .doc format (120 Acts), and some were only available as .rtf documents (11 Acts). The title of the documents varied also, some of them having an id according to the name (such as P18KX675), some of them according to their year (such as 1991-149) and some of them even a text form (such as AustAntarctic Territory 1954).

The title and a first id could be inferred from the document harvesting stage, the rest of the processing was done after parsing with the Apache POI library. Additional nicknames were extracted from the text when searching for patterns 'This Act may be cited as the' and 'This Act is' within a paragraph entitled 'Short Title'. The articles were extracted after the table of contents was identified. The title of each article is preceded by an ordinal number which facilitated the extraction.

During the extracting of the different components of every Act, an RDF Jena model was created and populated. The schema of reference was the one of ELI Ontology⁹, whose base URL is: <<http://data.europa.eu/eli/ontology#>> .

A total of 884 documents could be transformed without major incident. The transformation of all the documents lasts about 18 minutes using a standard laptop.

6.3. Portal development

A minimal portal to visualize data has been set up and it is available under the following URL:

<http://idt-skynet.uab.cat:8080/portal>

The server is located at Universitat Autònoma de Barcelona, within the IDT group.¹⁰ The portal (Figure 4. CRC demo portal) shows a list of documents, paginated in groups of ten. There is a search form to refine the list

⁹ https://eur-lex.europa.eu/eli-register/news_item_9.html

¹⁰ This server has been set up for internal purposes and it is not granted to work after the development has finished.

CRC demo portal

This is a temporal demonstration related to the CRC project. This is for internal purposes --not to be disclosed.

Jurisdiction

10 ▾

Resources

[Security Treaty \(Australia, New Zealand and the United States of America\) Act 1952](#)

[Appropriation Act \(No. 3\) 2017-2018](#)

[Qantas Airways Limited \(Loan Guarantee\) Act 1984](#)

[Protection of Cultural Objects on Loan Act 2013](#)

[Anti-Personnel Mines Convention Act 1998](#)

[Radiocommunications \(Transitional Provisions and Consequential Amendments\) Act 1992](#)

[Health Workforce Australia \(Abolition\) Act 2014](#)

[Federal Financial Relations Act 2009](#)

[Petroleum and Other Fuels Reporting Act 2017](#)

Figure 4. CRC demo portal

Besides the portal, and given that the mere transformation of the Australian legislation is a result of this project, the dataset has been published in Zenodo¹¹ and can be cited with a permanent DOI (Rodríguez-Doncel, 2018).

6.4. Text analytics

Whereas any meaningful analysis of the Australian legislation texts is beyond the scope of this project, even for the restricted case of spent convictions, some first insights were made using basic information retrieval techniques (TF-IDF [Ramos 2003]) topic modelling and the IBM Watson Natural Language Understanding (NLU) service¹².

Extraction of keywords and concepts

Keyword is understood in this document to mean any term (single or multi-word) with significance from an information retrieval (IR) point of view. A concept is defined by the set of terms (and their frequency) which declare it, in this case in Wikipedia.

Using the IBM NLU keyword extraction method over a non-specific model (Wikipedia for English), results were of interest (see Table 2) for the document

¹¹ <http://zenodo.org>

¹² <https://www.ibm.com/watson/services/natural-language-understanding/>

identified 336, whereas concepts (see Table 3) were of lesser interest. The most interesting entries have been marked in red colour. Similar results are shown for case 286, with keywords (Table 4) and concepts (Table 5, this time omitting the related Wikipedia page). Similar results are obtained using TF-IDF against a similar model –but IBM Watson is easier to use especially for the multi-word case.

relevance	keyword
0.6727	Judiciary Act
0.6571	permanent protection visa class XA
0.6110	conviction orders
0.6008	cl 866.222A of the Migration Regulations
0.5909	judicial review of a decision of the respondent
0.5832	s 85ZL
0.5781	orders of the Court of Petty Sessions
0.5684	temporary protection visa
0.5631	grant of a subclass
0.5626	Judicial Review
0.5470	convictions
0.5437	law of a State
0.5425	respect of an application
0.5374	protection visa
0.5364	s 39B of the Judiciary Act
0.5349	applicant
0.5346	purposes of cl 866.222A of the Regulations
0.5297	Migration Act
0.5285	Refugee Review Tribunal
0.5283	Western Australia

Table 2. Keywords extracted for the document 336

relevance	concept	wikipedia equivalent
0.9578	Crime	http://dbpedia.org/resource/Crime
0.6769	Conviction	http://dbpedia.org/resource/Conviction
0.5799	Criminal law	http://dbpedia.org/resource/Criminal_law
0.5518	Legal terms	http://dbpedia.org/resource/Legal_terms
0.4305	Summary offence	http://dbpedia.org/resource/Summary_offence
0.4046	Commonwealth of Australia laws	http://dbpedia.org/resource/Commonwealth_of_Australia_laws
0.4018	Not proven	http://dbpedia.org/resource/Not_proven

Table 3. Concepts extracted for the document 336

relevance	keyword
0.7782	appellant spent conviction orders
0.6787	decision of a magistrate
0.6040	Magistrates Court
0.5983	number of drug offences
0.5764	conviction order
0.5565	serious nature of the offences
0.5558	decision of the magistrate
0.5480	conviction orders
0.5459	nature of the appellant
0.5435	Sentencing Act
0.5432	Magistrates' discretion
0.5390	granting of an Aviation Security Identification Card
0.5331	Civil Aviation Safety Authority

0.5315	seriousness of the offences
0.5307	State of Western Australia
0.5302	number of character references
0.5302	adverse criminal record
0.5300	adverse effect
0.5236	appellant's counsel
0.5231	quantity of the drugs

Table 4. Keywords extracted for the document 286

relevance	concept	relevance	concept
0.9652	Crime	0.4273	Adverse effect
0.6477	Conviction	0.4265	Drug
0.5540	Criminal law	0.4244	Law
0.4811	Appeal	0.4195	Not proven
0.4720	Drug addiction	0.4149	Magistrate
0.4600	Summary offence	0.4067	Felony
0.4346	Judge	0.3962	Pilot licensing in the United Kingdom

Table 5. Concepts extracted for the document 286

The TF-IDF matrix can also be used to determine the similarity between two documents. As a small exercise, the cosine similarity was calculated between four of the judgments described above (128, 286, 336, 765). The pair “128 – Frugtniet” and “765 - Volonski” is the most similar (Table 6), although these cases were disjoint enough for the results to be not truly meaningful.

	128	286	336	765
128				
286	0.044			
336	0.020	0.069		
765	0.093	0.022	0.021	

Table 6. Cosine similarity between four judgments

7. Conclusions

After having drawn a roadmap and having explored each of the proposed stages, the following conclusions can be drawn.

First, that Australian Federal Legislation is open and ready to be exploited. Federal legislation in Australia is published with an open license (CC-BY) freely available. Although obtaining massive data is technically non-trivial, nothing prevents a massive download –and a massive download was made during the course of this project.

This is the first effort to publish Australian Federal Legislation as a bulk file for download both in TXT and TTL forms –making the resource very important to NLP experts, linguists and in general to any party interested in computer informatics.

The publication of Australian law as TTL resembling the European standards is a major outcome of this project because it embodies the idea of *law as data*. Once *law is data*, the possibilities offered by new NLP techniques can be fully exploited.

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